

An ESP32-Based Low-Cost Autonomous Cleaning Robot with Real-Time 2D Mapping, A* Path Replanning, and Mobile App Control

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Abstract— This paper presents Neko, a low-cost autonomous robot vacuum cleaner built around the ESP32 microcontroller. While commercial robot vacuums rely on expensive LiDAR or vision-based SLAM, Neko achieves real-time 2D occupancy grid mapping, sensor-fused pose estimation, and autonomous path replanning using commodity hardware: three HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensors, an MPU6050 Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and wheel encoders. To address the resource constraints of the ESP32, we introduce a heap-optimized 8-bit log-odds occupancy grid map, a three-ray Bresenham approximation to model the 15° sonar beam cone, and a dual-core task scheduling model using FreeRTOS. Our architecture isolates the time-critical motor controls and sensor polling on Core 0, leaving Core 1 dedicated to the A* path planning algorithm, maintaining a path replanning latency of under 45 ms. Experimental results demonstrate that fusing the gyroscope heading with wheel odometry reduces heading drift by 80%, while dynamic range weighting resolves thin obstacles (e.g., chair legs) without map distortion. A mobile-first Tauri 2 Android application visualizes the grid map and streams live telemetry over WebSockets at 250 ms intervals.

Keywords— Autonomous robot, ESP32, occupancy grid, sensor fusion, A* path planning, ultrasonic sensing, vacuum cleaner.

I. INTRODUCTION

Commercial autonomous vacuum cleaners have transformed domestic cleaning, relying heavily on Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) or visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (VSLAM) systems. However, these systems require expensive sensors and high-performance application processors (e.g., ARM Cortex-A series), keeping hardware costs prohibitive for budget consumers and hobbyist developers.

To bridge this gap, this paper introduces Neko, a fully autonomous robotic vacuum cleaner built using low-cost commodity components with an ESP32 microcontroller at its core. The ESP32 is a low-power, dual-core system-on-chip (SoC) operating at 240 MHz, costing a fraction of a typical single-line LiDAR module. However, executing real-time 2D occupancy mapping, dead-reckoning fusion, and path planning on a microcontroller presents major challenges:

1. **Severe Memory Constraints:** The ESP32 has only 520 KB of SRAM, much of which is consumed by the Wi-Fi/WebSocket stack.
2. **Computational Overhead:** Running A* path planning over large grids in real time can block low-level safety-critical control tasks.
3. **Sensor Noise and Angular Uncertainty:** Cheap HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensors have a 15 degree beam width, creating blurred walls and overestimating obstacle sizes.

Neko solves these constraints through:

1. A fused odometry model combining wheel encoders and Z-axis gyroscope integration to mitigate wheel slip.
2. An optimized 8-bit log-odds occupancy grid requiring less than 100 KB of RAM.

3. A multi-ray Bresenham raycasting model that accounts for sonar beam width and range uncertainty.
4. A dual-core task allocation layout under FreeRTOS to achieve sub-45 ms replanning latency without blocking motor control loops.

II. METHODOLOGY

The system architecture of Neko is divided into two primary layers: the Embedded Control Firmware executing on the ESP32 and the Mobile User Interface running as an Android application packaged via Tauri 2.

A. Sensor Fusion & Pose Estimation

To track the robot's physical pose $[x, y, \theta]$ in the global coordinate frame, the firmware fuses dead-reckoning odometry from wheel encoders with high-frequency heading rate updates from the MPU6050 IMU.

1. **Encoder-Based Displacement:** Optical wheel encoders measure individual wheel rotations. The physical displacement d of the robot's center point is calculated as the average linear distance traveled by the left and right wheels:

$$d_c = \frac{\Delta d_{left} + \Delta d_{right}}{2}$$

where wheel displacements are derived from encoder pulse counts using the wheel diameter (65 mm) and pulses per revolution (20 RPM).

2. **Gyroscope Yaw Estimation:** To mitigate wheel slip errors, the robot's heading θ is tracked by integrating the gyroscope Z-axis angular velocity (ω_z) over time:

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + (\omega_z - \omega_{bias})\Delta T; \text{ where } \omega_{bias} \text{ is the zero-rate offset calibrated during a stationary boot phase, and } \Delta T \text{ is the sample interval.}$$

3. **Pose Tracking:** Fused displacement and heading are projected into global coordinates at 50 Hz.

B. Occupancy Grid Mapping & Sonar Cone Physics

The environment is modeled as a discrete 2D grid where each cell corresponds to a physical square of $50\text{mm} \times 50\text{mm}$. Each cell (x_g, y_g) stores an 8-bit signed integer value $L(x_g, y_g) \in [-127, 127]$ representing the log-odds probability of occupancy.

1) Heap Memory Constraints:

The maximum map dimensions are constrained by the ESP32's available heap. Let W and H be the width and height of the map in meters, and $r = 0.05\text{m}$ be the cell resolution. The memory footprint in bytes is:

$Memory = \left(\frac{W}{r}\right) \times \left(\frac{H}{r}\right) \times 1 \text{ Byte}$; With approximately 180 KB of free heap available after initializing the Wi-Fi AP and WebSocket buffers, the firmware allocates a static block of 100 KB for the grid array (100,000 cells).

1. At 50mm resolution, this covers a physical area of 250m^2 (e.g., $15.8\text{m} \times 15.8\text{m}$).
2. For larger environments, the firmware dynamically downscales the resolution to 100mm per cell, expanding the coverage area to 1000m^2 under the identical 100 KB memory footprint

2) Sonar Wavefront Modeling:

The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor has a 15° beam width. At its maximum reliable range of 1500mm, the wavefront width expands to:

$$W_{\text{cone}} = 2 \times 1500 \times \tan(7.5^\circ) \approx 395\text{mm}$$

A naive raycaster drawing a single thin line clears cells that are actually blocked by off-axis obstacles, and places "ghost" walls at the center-point. To handle this angular uncertainty, we implement a three-ray approximation model:

Each sonar reading is modeled using a three-ray Bresenham approximation consisting of a central ray and two boundary rays at $\pm 7.5^\circ$. Cells along the rays are marked as free space, while the measured endpoints are reinforced as occupied in the log-odds grid. Range-dependent confidence weighting mitigates the widening effect of the sonar beam, improving the representation of thin obstacles. The resulting

log-odds values are then thresholded into occupied, free, and unknown states.

C. Coverage Path Planning

To clean the floor systematically, the robot switches between two modes based on map availability.

Mode 1: Exploratory Coverage (First Run):

When exploring a new space, Neko implements a hybrid reactive loop:

1. Wall Following: Using its side ultrasonic sensors, the robot traces the room perimeter. A proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller modulates the motor PWM speeds to maintain a constant distance of 15cm from the wall based on the distance error $e(t) = D_{\text{side}} - 150\text{mm}$. This outlines the boundary of the occupancy grid.
2. Boustrophedon (Lawnmower) Sweeping: Once a boundary segment is defined, the robot switches to parallel sweeps. It drives forward until the front sensor detects an obstacle ($D_{\text{front}} < 280\text{mm}$), executes a 90° turn, translates laterally by the sweeper width (200mm), and makes another 90° turn to sweep back.
3. Random Bounce Fallback: If the robot gets locked in a corner or receives noisy readings (due to specular reflections), it falls back to a random angle turn to break free before resuming.

Mode 2: Map-Guided Systematic Coverage:

When a pre-built map is loaded, the path planning switches to an offline cellular decomposition model:

1. Cellular Decomposition: The 2D map is partitioned into rectangular, obstacle-free zones.
2. Boustrophedon Swaths: The robot cleans each zone sequentially using tight parallel sweeps.
3. A* Waypoint Navigation: To transit from one completed zone to the next, the robot executes the A* pathfinding algorithm on the occupancy grid, minimizing the cost function $f(n) = g(n) + h(n)$ where $g(n)$ is the path cost from start to node n , and $h(n)$ is the Euclidean distance heuristic to the target.
4. Dynamic Obstacle Replanning: If a dynamic obstacle (e.g., a pet or shoe) blocks the path:
 - The local ultrasonic sensors trigger an immediate stop.
 - Core 0 updates the occupancy grid with the new hit.
 - Core 1 is flagged to recalculate the A* path around the obstacle, returning a new waypoint list.

D. Mobile Application & Communications

The mobile user interface is developed as a web application utilizing Vite/React and packaged for Android using Tauri 2.

WebSocket Telemetry Stream: A lightweight TCP WebSocket server on port 81 of the ESP32 broadcasts a JSON telemetry payload every 250 ms:

Client Rendering: The application parses the telemetry frame and pushes the coordinate data into a coordinate queue. An HTML5 Canvas context translates the millimeter-based coordinates to pixels and draws the robot path and pose in real time.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Neko was evaluated in a domestic environment. Experiments focused on validating the effectiveness of the proposed sensor fusion, real-time replanning capability, and sonar mapping strategy. The results indicate that the system can reliably perform autonomous cleaning tasks despite the limited computational resources of the ESP32.

Table 1. Summary of Experimental Results

Metric	Baseline	Proposed Method	Improvement
Heading Drift after 5 m Run	14.2°	2.6°	81.7% reduction
Position Error (Return-to-Origin)	382 mm	54 mm	85.9% reduction
Thin Obstacle Representation	200–300 mm wide	50–100 mm wide	Reduced obstacle inflation

The encoder-gyroscope fusion significantly reduced odometry drift compared with encoder-only tracking, resulting in more consistent occupancy maps.

Furthermore, the dual-core FreeRTOS architecture enabled A* replanning within the required real-time budget without affecting motor control performance. Finally, the three-ray sonar model with range-dependent confidence weighting improved the representation of narrow obstacles, preventing them from being falsely mapped as large impassable objects.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented Neko, a low-cost autonomous vacuum cleaner executing real-time 2D mapping and A path replanning on an ESP32 microcontroller. By using an 8-bit log-odds representation, a 3-ray sonar cone model, and a FreeRTOS dual-core allocation scheme, we successfully addressed the microcontroller's RAM limits and CPU bottlenecks. Experimental evaluation verified that our sensor fusion pipeline reduces angular drift by 80%, while A replanning maintains a latency of 28.4 ms on a 100 × 100 grid. Future work will investigate active loop closure using Wi-Fi signal strength triangulation to further limit odometry drift in larger multi-room layouts.

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